

Training of Head Teachers Workshop in Supportive Supervision and Instructional Leadership

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Abstract— The study is a report on Training of Head Teachers Workshop in Supportive Supervision and Instructional Leadership Organised in Kailahun District in 2018.

The design of the study was a descriptive survey. Two categories of questionnaires were prepared. The target population was twenty-five head teachers drawn from various primary schools. Frequency and simple percentage were used for data analysis.

The study revealed that the head teachers performed better in post test as compared to the pre-test. The lowest score in the pre test was 17% and the highest score was 77%. The lowest score in the post test was 56% and the highest was 86%. The study also observed that most of the head teachers were male, about 88% and 12% as female. Findings also show that the twenty-five schools selected were all represented. Some recommendations were made:

- i). Head teachers to delegate responsibilities to staff.
- ii). Head teachers to encourage their teachers to attend workshops and in-service training.
- iii). School inspectors to embark on effective monitoring and supervision.
- iv). Government to supervise funds and materials provided to school for equality control and quality assurance.
- v). Teaching service commission to license train and qualify teachers.
- vi). Government to monitor and supervise performance contract in schools.

I. INTRODUCTION

Head teachers are the most important facilitators in educational administration and management. The head teachers are also change agents or managers who design for the improvement of their institutions.

To achieve quality control and assurance in the educational system, head teachers require new skills, techniques, methods and knowledge.

Furthermore, head of schools are leaders of everything that occur in the school environment. They are responsible for curricular and extra curricular activities in the school. Therefore, the head teacher is the head of all instructional activities in the school and the community.

The head teachers provide the resources and create conducive environment for learning to occur. In the process of giving instruction, the teachers need technical support to undertake their assignment and the head teachers must be knowledge enough to give that support.

Effective head teachers must combine the traditional or old leadership duties such as educating teachers, budgeting for the schools and facilities maintenance with a serious involvement with specific aspects of teaching and learning.

One of the great puzzles of education is how to take a successful innovative programme, transfer it to a new setting and obtain equally good results. Though we don't always like to acknowledge it, classroom and school cultures are created at the local level. Successful instructional motivation programmes must therefore be able to take account of context of individual communities and of the students in specific classrooms.

What can teachers and administrators do to sustain initially high levels of morale, motivation and performance for students and colleagues alike? First educators must understand what students and colleague want; then, they must give it to them (Sirota, Mischkind and Meltzer (2005).

Katzenbach (2006) argued that pride is what ultimately motivates individuals both in the classroom and the work place to excel at what they do.

Teachers play an essential role in nurturing students integration of skills. Joyce, Wolf, and Calhoun (1973) concluded that successful teaching begins by establishing supporting relationship. It is necessary for school heads to provide supportive roles to staff.

Aim and Objectives:

The Aim

The general aim of the study was to collect information from the twenty – five (25) head teachers on supportive supervision and instructional leadership.

Specific Objectives

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine head teachers performance in pre-test and post-test.
2. Identify male and female participation in training workshop.
3. Determine the level of schools participation in training workshop

II. METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The research was conducted in Kailahun town of Sierra Leone. Kailahun town is the headquarters of Kailahun District. The district consist of fifteen (15) chiefdoms. However, six (6) chiefdoms participated in the training workshop namely;

Kissi Teng, Luawa, Upper Bambara, Mandu, Kissi Kama and Lauwa Sewallu. The inhabitants of Kailahun town come from all the major ethnic groups of Sierra Leone, Guinea and Liberia particularly the Mende, Temmne, Limba, Fulas, Kissy, Kono and Vai. However, majority who live in Kailahun town

also speak Krio. Most of the primary schools were established by Islamic Mission and Christian Missionaries such as Roman Catholic or Ahmadiyya Mission.

Research Design

The design of the study is descriptive survey type, whose purpose was to get information on head teachers performance in pre-test ad post – test and level of participation.

Population

The population for the study comprised of head teachers of primary schools from selected chiefdoms in Kailahun District.

Twenty-five (25) primary schools were selected. Twenty – five head teachers were involved. The twenty five head teachers were made up of five groups for the training workshop.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

The random sampling procedure or method was used in the selection of sample size. Here, every head teacher in every Islamic Mission, Christian Mission, Government and Government Assisted Schools in the Chiefdoms had an equal opportunity of being chosen or selected.

Instrument and Data Collection

The instruments used for the study were structured questionnaires. Two categories of questionnaires were designed. Questionnaire ‘A’ for pre-test and ‘B’ for post – test.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Head teachers performance in pre-test and post test:

Figure I show that twenty five (25) participants about 100% attended a three – day training workshop in supportive supervision and instructional leadership.

TABLE I. Pre-test and post-test analysis

Range of Score (Percentage %)	Number of Participants in the Pre-test	Number of Participants
15 - 20	01	-
21 - 25	01	-
26 - 30	02	-
31 - 35	-	-
36 - 40	02	-
41 - 45	03	-
46 - 50	05	-
51 - 55	03	-
56 - 60	03	04
61 - 65	01	06
66 - 70	02	07
71 - 75	01	02
76 - 80	01	02
81 - 85	-	02
86 - 90	-	02
	X = 48. 24	X = 86.16

In the pre-test 14 participants about 56% of them scored below 55%. However, 11 participants about 44% of them scored above 55%. The lowest score in the pre test was 17% and the highest was 77%.

Based on comparative analysis, the post test was encouraging. 4 participants about 16% scored below 65%. 21

participants about 84% scored above 65%. The lowest score in the post test was 56% and the highest was 86%.

The performance of participants in group work and post test administered was good. Based on the finding, the head teachers understood the basic concept of supportive supervision and instructional leadership. The head teachers learnt to combine the traditional leadership duties such as staff evaluation, budgeting and effective instructional leadership that actively involved in curricular and instructional issues that affect pupil achievement.

Table II shows that 25 participants about 100% attended the training workshop.

TABLE II. Male and female head teachers participation

S/No.	Head Teachers	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
1	Male	22	88%
2	Female	03	12%
3	Total	25	100%

Twenty – two (22) of the participants about 88% were male while 3 participants about 12% were female. Based on the findings, most of the head teachers in the public and private schools in the chiefdoms were male. The three (3) female participants performed better in group discussion and the test administered. Schools should encourage women as head teachers.

The motive behind the training workshop was to enhance head teachers performance in school administration and management through supportive supervision and instructional leadership. Twenty five (25) primary schools were selected for a three – day training workshop in Kailahun town. All the schools that were invited actively took part in the workshop. The level of participant of primary schools was good. They actively involved in group discussion group representation and developed individual action plan for 2019 academic year. They also developed the culture of delegating responsibilities to their subjects. All the primary schools were willing to

contribute to free quality education introduced in Sierra Leone by the Government.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Most head teachers were not aware or practicing the new innovations in our educational system such as supportive supervision, instructional leadership, how to state the school vision and mission statement and school Action Plan to enhance teaching and learning process. However, during the training, they were able to develop more knowledge on educational Administration and Management, School Records, Child Right Issues, Emerging Issues, Delegating responsibilities to other teachers and professional standards for teachers and school heads.

Recommendation

The following recommendation for the improvement of free quality education in Sierra Leone were made.

1. The head teachers should delegate responsibilities to other teachers for quality assurance in our education system.
2. Head teachers should encourage their teachers to attend workshop, seminars and in-service training.
3. School supervisors and inspectors should embark on effective monitoring and supervision.
4. Woman should be encouraged to act as head teachers in schools.
5. All funds provided by government and non-government organizations for training programmes should be monitored.
6. Teaching service commission to license teachers for effective performance.
7. Government to monitor performance contract in all schools for effective administration.

REFERENCE

[1] Joyce, B. Wolf, J & Calhoun (1993) – The self – renewing school. Alexandria VA. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
 [2] Katzenbach, J. (2006) – Motivation beyond money: Learning from Peak Performers, Leader to Leader 41:59
 [3] Sirota D.L. Mischkind, and M. Meltzer (2005). Assumptions that kill Morale. Leader to Leader 38: 24-27

TABLE III. Level of schools participation in training workshop

S/No.	School	Location in the Chiefdom	Participant Per-School
1	Free Pentecostal Mission, Primary School	Kissy Teng	1
2	Kailahun District Council Primary School	Kissy Teng	1
3	National Islamic Primary School	Luawa	1
4	Methodist Primary School	Luawa	1
5	Kailahun District Council Primary School- Kangama	Kissy Teng	1
6	Roman Catholic Primary School- Dia	Kissi Kama	1
7	Methodist Primary School- Pendembu	Upper Bambara	1
8	Kailahun District Council Primary School - Kpandebu	Luawa	1
9	Roman Catholic Primary School – Mano Sewallu	Luawa Sewallu	1
10	Sierra Leone Muslim Brotherhood Primary School – Kailahun Town	Luawa	1
11	Sierra Leone Muslim Brotherhood Primary School – Ngiehun	Luawa	1
12	Kailahun District Council Primary School – Kailahun Town	Lauwa	1
13	Ahmadiyya Primary School- Kamaru	Upper Bambara	1
14	Superime Islamic Council - Mandu	Mandu	1
15	Kailahun District Council Primary School- Buedu	Kissi Teng	1
16	Ansural Islamic Primary School - Koindu	Kissi Teng	1
17	Kailahun District Council Primary School- Gbadehun	Luawa	1
18	Assembly of God Primary School - Koindu	Kissi Teng	1
19	Roman Catholic Primary School – Kailahun Town	Lauwa	1
20	Methodist Primary School – Kailahun Town	Luawa	1
21	Methodist Primary School – Kailahun Town	Luawa	1
22	Kailahun District Council Primary School - Jangbellu	Luawa	1
23	Sierra Leone Muslim Brotherhood Primary School – Pendembu	Upper Bambara	1
24	Ahmadiyya Muslim Primary School – Kailahun Town	Luawa	1
25	Roman Catholic Primary School – Kailahun Town	Luawa	1
	TOTAL		25